

ABSTRACT

Social work as a discipline stands out owing to its inherently interdisciplinary nature. Feminist studies also transcend disciplinary boundaries. However, despite such an overbearing characteristic that underlines them, somehow feminist perspectives in social work had been a laggard. Since women are a majority in the social work profession, the assumption that it will naturally entail due care of feminist scholarship is a misnomer. This article looks at the unity between social work and feminist approaches and how new epistemological changes within social work itself has opened up new vistas for feminist social work. It advocates an epistemological continuum along which feminist social work must tread.

Keywords: *Feminist social work, interdisciplinary, epistemological continuum, reflexivity*

Social Work Research and Feminism

Social work as a discipline has grown beyond our imagination and now encompasses issues of extreme contemporary relevance. Michael Reisch(2019) notes that these can range from economic, demographic, and cultural aspects to something as colossal as climate change. Social workers, therefore, had to relook at their functioning, whether it was in terms of organised social welfare or its zeal to enhance its professional status. The fallouts of neoliberalism and anti-welfare proponents had to be countered. Just as social work was evolving, so was feminism.

Research on women’s issues did not always have a feminist angle in social work. However, contemporary understandings of social work have changed and embraced the notion that women’s problems concern women and the larger society. Laura Bronstein (2003) notes that social work has been interdisciplinary right from the beginning. Molly Strothmann(2010)also adds that social work research and education focus primarily on other fields' literature. Joan Orme (1998), in her essay on “Feminist Social Work”, contends that historically. However, social work engaged more women in the profession, both as providers and users of the social services, adopting a gendered approach has been relatively recent. She notes that Horobin (1987), in “Sex, Gender, and Care Work”, tried to understand the

gendered underpinnings in policy and legislation and how it can impact social work practice. However, much remained uncovered under the contemporary feminist perspectives. Orme(1998)informs that most research was stereotypical in their interpretations concerning men and women and their roles and behaviour in society. Feminist social work set the ground for change within the discipline. Barbara Collins (1986) also asserted that social work is essentially feminist, and that must be brought to the fore. She further laid out how the ethos and value systems of social work and feminism are concurrent to each other. Both perspectives talk about transcending dichotomy; and advocate anti-compartmentalization of knowledge and an interdisciplinary knowledge base.

Epistemological Changes Within Social Work

Anita Gibbshighlights the economic and political undercurrents are sweeping upon social work theory and practice, thus resulting in epistemic restructuring. She also emphasises practitioners' role as researchers note the vast array of literature on research epistemology, paradigms, discussions on social work practice as a profession and as a body of knowledge. She underlines

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how feminist research considers the gendered nature of social work and deconstructs knowledge bases and societal structures within the mainframe of social work research. Feminists advocate the active participation of women as researchers and as the researched. Women bearing the burden of welfare work, oppressive and sexist institutional practices, the need to promote women-centred practices are also advocated as thrust areas (Gibbs, 2001).

Stephen Hicks (2015) reiterates that social work must further gender and make it integral to it. He laments how social work is misconstrued as a female-dominated profession, whereas contrarily, the women are actually 'handled' by men. Hicks, therefore, cites Orme (2001), who refuted looking at femininity and masculinity as dichotomous opposites. Hence, engendering gender within social work is pertinent.

An Epistemological Continuum

Gita Mehrotra (2010) advocates that intersectionality serves as a suitable framework to understand multiple identities and the interconnectedness of oppressive systems in women's lives. She suggests that such a multiplicity can be viewed and examined better if feminist social work scholars work on an intersectionality continuum. A range of epistemologies can be purposefully applied to suit the research problem's nature, time, and context. Interdisciplinary feminist scholarship looks at a web of oppressive factors, multiple identities, and the social inequalities in women's lives. Feminist social work scholars are likewise increasingly focussing on this multiplicity of experience, social positionality, and context.

What is noteworthy is that Mehrotra's (2010) proposal of an intersectionality continuum has an overarching reach beyond that of race, class, and gender. She proposes including sexuality, ability, nation, and other facets of diversity and social identity. Social workers must understand that human subjects can undergo varying life experiences at different times ranging from being oppressed to being powerful. An epistemological

intersectional continuum helps capture the different contexts of space and time (Mehrotra, 2010).

Feminist social work and its focus on gender-based social justice, with women across diverse communities, help theorise a multiplicity of intersecting oppressions faced by women.

Mehrotra (2010) also notes the works of Collins (1990) and Hooks (1984), who challenged mainstream and dominant feminist notions of "woman". They expounded upon the inter-twined positions of race and gender oppression and women of colour's unique positionalities. There is also an emphasis on pluralism as an approach that can be tailored to meet the specificities of any social inquiry (Bohman, 1998; Borden, 2010; Orme, 2003). Such a pluralism can unearth hidden meanings of social phenomena that seem difficult to unravel. Adopting a range of paradigms will help adopt a multi-faceted approach to feminist social work and further facilitate critical inquiry (Mehrotra, 2010).

Feminist Methodology

The epistemology of what is knowledge is being severely challenged by feminists. What has always been belittled as women's stories are now resurging with vitality. Fonow and Cook (2005) emphasise the significance of intersectionality of gender with race, sexuality, and class. They also discuss the vexing problems of research at every step in justifying the rationale of feminist methodology. Thus, they focused on epistemology as the core. They emphasise an authentic voice to represent the diversities of diverse women who can also bridge theory and practice.

Fonow and Cook (2005) enlist a multitude of methods that feminist scholars employ. These range from autoethnography, biography, case study, content analysis, deconstruction, historiography, discourse analysis, ethnography, needs assessment, oral history, participant observation etc., to name a few. This reflects the diversity of approach and allows for reiteration of the

“epistemological continuum” advocated by Mehrotra (2010). Locating the female body as the site of oppression is an exemplary achievement in feminist scholarship. Reproductive rights, motherhood, rape, manipulating women’s bodies to promote popular youth culture have their pivot as the female body in feminist research (Fonow & Cook, 2005). This further spawned a varied range of epistemologies to studying the female body.

Walking the Epistemological Tightrope

Feminist approaches draw many parallels with social work. The emphasis on social action and policymaking is one of them. Feminists believe in actively partnering with their subjects. Just as social work accords a high value to participatory action research, feminists believe that such involvement of subjects can help erode the power hierarchy; and the resultant body of knowledge can bring about social change. However, in this earnestness to capture the authentic voices of the oppressed subjects, who are subsumed within an array of intersectional forces, the dilemma of quantitative versus qualitative methods prevail. Westmarland (2001) also notes how quantitative feminist research is breaking new ground by emphasising the need to be sensitive towards women’s experiences. The stark vulnerabilities of women, such as physical and sexual abuse that can burden their lives differently, are also noted. These are thus new vistas in feminist research across disciplines.

With these new waves sweeping quantitative research, what is now gaining strength is the triangulation method or what is referred to as the mixed method (Jenkins, 2000). Susan Hanson and Geraldine Pratt (1995) combined census data with in-depth interviews to understand the gender-wise occupation patterns in their study, thus successfully applying the mixed method (as cited in Fonow and Cook, 2005).

Conclusion

Feminism looks at the world through a distinctive approach. Despite their differences, Martin Hammersley

(1992) closely examines some common grounds that feminists tread upon. The first is gender as a central concern. Second is the premium according to experience in women’s lives. Thirdly, the researcher and research must be freed from a hierarchy. And fourthly, the overarching goal of feminist research is emancipation. Thus, in this multi-layered understanding of feminist scholarship, feminist social work research can find assistance by partnering with the research subjects themselves. Confronting social issues and enhancing societal well-being is the essence of social work. Feminist social work can further this plan by breaking the hierarchical glass ceiling. Indigenous research must be welcomed as it can generate a wealth of knowledge of the hitherto unknown in dominant research paradigms.

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